

Quality Culture Affecting Pupils' Satisfaction: A Case Study Of Public Secondary Schools In Ho Chi Minh City

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 07, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: June 06, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Quality, Culture, Public, University, And SGU</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4904766</p>	<p><i>Quality culture is a concern in public secondary schools. A culture of specific quality and suitable to each secondary school's context and development goals is a prerequisite for improving training and community service quality, creating a unique identity. And quality culture help enhancing the competitiveness of public secondary schools in the context of educational globalization. Therefore, this paper aims to determine quality culture affecting pupils' satisfaction at ten public secondary schools in Ho Chi Minh City (HCMC). The authors applied a simple random sampling technique. The authors tested Cronbach's Alpha and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and model testing with Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). Besides, the study surveyed 600 pupils and answered 27 questions, but 557 samples were processed. The study's findings had five factors affecting the quality culture, affecting pupils' satisfaction with a significance level of 0.01.</i></p>

Introduction

Many educators also mention quality culture since the concept of quality is particularly interested. In many countries, concepts such as 'quality,' 'quality assurance,' or 'quality inspection/audit' have become familiar terms by (Ahmed, A., & Nulland, Y. V., 2016). It is a fact that while schools/academic units care about quality, the majority of teachers and students appear indifferent or do not participate in these quality activities. According to (Ilze Kairiša, Inga L., 2019), the concept of 'quality culture' has been mentioned a lot recently when talking about the regular participation of teachers, staff, and learners in the activities of the training unit. However, it is essential to mention the concept of "culture" regarding a quality culture. In Vietnam, "culture" is understood as (1) In general, the material and spiritual values created by man in the historical process; (2) Human activities to satisfy the spiritual life needs; (3) Knowledge, scientific knowledge; (4) High proficiency in social activities, a manifestation of civilization (Culturally living; lack of culture; and (5) Culture of an ancient historical period, determined based on an overall, the found relics have the same characteristics.

From there is quality culture. Cultural interest as a tool for quality improvement in an organization is growing and being studied in many countries. 'Value-based management' is seen as a useful model that helps MANAGERS change how traditionally viewed rigid organizations move to a more flexible and flexible model to respond by (Kancikova, A., 2019). with the changes and demands, the increasing demands of society. In many countries, the connection between universities and social institutions is increasingly high, enterprise-based management models are increasingly being applied by many schools, including the value-based management model. (Kolhi, R., S., 2015) Also, there are many similarities between traditional and modern management, in which cultural factors, values, and beliefs of organizational members still play. Important role. When society changes, those changes always affect people, regardless of the environment. The European Universities Association (EUA) thinks that a quality culture is viewed based on two factors.

The first element of a quality culture is values, beliefs, and expectations towards quality. The second element, the management/structure element, has pre-defined quality assurance processes and collaborative efforts. The European Universities Association (EUA) thinks that a quality culture is viewed based on two factors. The first element of a quality culture is values, beliefs, and expectations towards quality. The second element, the management/structure element, has pre-defined quality assurance processes and cooperative efforts by (Mahmood, H., 2018). The European Universities Association (EUA) thinks that a quality culture is viewed based on two factors. The first element of a quality culture is values, beliefs, and expectations towards quality. The second element, the management/structure element, has pre-defined quality assurance processes and collaborative efforts.

According to (Martin Cepel, 2019), Quality culture can be said that the understanding and conception of quality culture is more associated with beliefs, values, and attitudes than knowledge, practical research, or analysis of quality processes, although there are many interconnections. The link between these factors. In other words, to understand and build a quality culture, it is necessary to influence understanding, regulation/organization, and management measures, and the views and beliefs about people's values to join in the organization. Besides, organizational culture is also not an intangible concept; it is formed in the framework of an organization/institution and has a basis, limitation, and relationships with many other factors by (Mozanai, M., & Ling, G. Y., 2017). This study aims to determine the factors affecting the quality culture, affecting pupils' satisfaction at public secondary schools in Ho Chi Minh City. These results help educational managers apply the research results to improve the quality culture and pupils' satisfaction better in the future.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The quality culture (QC)

According to (Mihai Adrian Valcea, 2014), Quality culture is a part of organizational culture: habits, practices, beliefs, and values associated with quality. There is a negative culture in terms of quality, such as the habit of concealing mistakes, defects, or a positive culture like trying to satisfy customers. The quality of education is the top concern of society, especially in the trend of international integration. Educational institutions must create or build for themselves the core values of a quality culture for sustainable development.

According to (Athena Xenikou, 2019) aims to improve the training quality of higher education institutions. The improvement of post-accreditation activities' quality should be done regularly and substantially, demonstrating the institution's commitment and accountability - a college education. Educational institutions need to raise awareness and capacity on quality assurance for stakeholders to build and develop a quality culture in schools.

According to (Naala, N. I., 2016) showed that by building a quality cultural environment, educational institutions would carry out the education and training industry's mission and goals to encourage all people to work and learn, dedicate their strength and mind. Your wisdom for the institution. Currently, the socio-cultural environment follows the development trend of the market economy and globalization. The school culture is also greatly affected, so the educational institution's organizational culture should be oriented to build by (Naureen, R., 2020). A quality culture is to indeed exert its positive influence on all members of the organization. Creating a quality culture at some of the above activities, but building a quality culture, is essentially setting up an environmental system for quality activities and continually improving the organization's quality by (Nife, J., D., 2016).

Academic environment (AE)

According to (Okoli, M., 2019), the Academic environment is the environment in which academic activities occur: teaching and learning, research, intellectual exchange, and advanced research and educational methods. The training programs of the public secondary schools are built. The modules' detailed schedule is periodically updated, adjusted according to society's development, and reflects the business's needs. Annually organize school-level lecturing associations and send lecturers to attend school-level lectures to exchange lecture design methods, teaching methods by (Smit, J., A., 2016). According to (Tang, J., and Stensaker, B., 2018), information on training and scientific research is regularly updated on the faculty's website, ensuring complete and timely information to stakeholders. Annually, nearly 100% of staff and lecturers in the school participate in learning to improve their professional qualifications and skills and attend scientific conferences and conferences by (Berings, D., Beerten, Z., Hulpiau, L.V., & Verhesschen, P., 2017). Learners are facilitated to develop their knowledge and skills in Olympic competitions, skills competitions, scientific research, and academic clubs. With the above-mentioned financial capacity, the researchers have hypothesis following:

Hypothesis H1: Academic environment has a positive impact on the quality culture of public secondary schools in Ho Chi Minh City.

Social environment (SE)

According to (Tewodros Bayeh Tedla, 2016), the Social environment is the environment in which social relationships, including the organizational framework, operational framework of the educational institution, and its members' behavior, are established and adjusted. Functions and tasks of the school are fully built and regularly updated according to new studies. The school, department, faculty, and specialist boards' responsibilities and powers are delimited and have quality assessment mechanisms by (Thomas, P., and Pyrros, P., 2018). (Trowler, M., and Cooper, N., 2019) showed that the document system for organizing and solving work is unified and applied in the whole department. Officers and officials in the faculty have a firm grasp of the regulations, understand their responsibilities and powers, are always conscious, and try to complete the

assigned tasks with the proper plan and quality by (Truwsock, N., and Andree, T., 2016). For the above-mentioned human resources, the researchers have hypothesis following:

Hypothesis H2: Social environment positively impacts the quality culture of public secondary schools in Ho Chi Minh City.

Humanistic environment (HE)

According to (Vettori, Oliver, and et. al., 2017), the humanistic environment is the environment in which members' and stakeholders' rights and obligations are established transparently and followed. Public secondary schools create favorable conditions for lecturers to develop deep expertise. (Wilkesmann, S., and Schmid, P., 2018) studied that effectively implement mechanisms, policies, and solutions for officials, employees, and learners to fully implement, with quality and responsibility towards the school and society. Schools continued building a spirit of solidarity and cohesion within the faculty, between disciplines, and the organization and community (Whalen, T., 2020). Learners are considered the subjects that are served, cared for wholeheartedly, thoughtfully in learning, living, and handling work by (Yorke, R., and Mantz, D. C., 2017). The technology mentioned above capability, the researchers, have hypothesis following:

Hypothesis H3: Humanistic environment positively impacts the quality culture of public secondary schools in Ho Chi Minh City.

Cultural environment (CE)

According to (Zake, M., and Lazim, H. M., 2015), the Cultural environment is the environment in which all people accept the set of standards, values, beliefs, and standards of conduct. Building an educational setting is to make school culture by (Christine Sattler and Karlheinz Sonntag, 2018). It is a green - clean - beautiful, safe, natural environment; a humane social environment with friendly and healthy relationships. School is a place to provide learners with new and modern knowledge and a cultural environment. (Christine S. and Karlheinz S., 2020). They are studied not to confuse educational attainment and cultural level in its academic and training mission. Each school should have steps and ways to build an educational environment in their unit to suit the school's characteristics and the school culture's nature by (Esther N., 2016). The researchers have hypothesis following:

Hypothesis H4: Cultural environment has a positive impact on the quality culture of public secondary schools in Ho Chi Minh City.

Natural environment (NAE)

According to (Abdulcalder, A., 2015), the natural environment is the landscape environment and facilities contributing to ensure and improve the quality of the higher education institution's operations. (Alamri, A. S., Cristea, A. I. and Al-Zaidi, M. S., 2014) studied that the natural environment for training and scientific research insufficient, quality, and used in an economical, safe and efficient manner. Working rooms, practice rooms/laboratories are regularly equipped, supplemented, and updated with new equipment and technologies to meet the Industrial 4.0 era's requirements by (Alomiri, H., 2016). Public secondary schools regularly cooperate with enterprises to create more environments for lecturers, students, and students to participate in learning and scientific research by (Aramina, D. M., 2015). The things mentioned above, the researchers have the following hypothesis. With the management as mentioned above capability, the researchers have theory following:

Hypothesis H5: Natural environment has a positive impact on the quality culture of public secondary schools in Ho Chi Minh City.

Hypothesis H6: Quality culture positively impacts the pupils' satisfaction with public secondary schools in Ho Chi Minh City.

Source: Researchers proposed

Figure 1.A research model for factors affecting the quality culture and pupils’ satisfaction of public secondary schools in Ho Chi Minh City

METHODS OF RESEARCH

Research methods are in the paper, including a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods.

Source: Researchers proposed

Figure 2.A research process for factors affecting the quality culture and pupils’ satisfaction of public secondary schools in Ho Chi Minh City

The authors had synthesized secondary data sources from documents, books, magazines, websites. The data got from statistical agencies, excess benefit from research projects related to the topic, and annual reports. Primary data is information and data collected through surveys and consultations with 15 leaders and educational management experts. The paper also used many different research methods by (Hair, B., B., & Anderson, 2010).

The researchers surveyed the completed questionnaires directly collected from the pupils related to 10 public secondary schools in Ho Chi Minh City. The authors applied a simple random sampling technique. The authors tested Cronbach’s Alpha and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and model testing with Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). The study surveyed 600 pupils and answered 27 questions, but 557 samples were processed, 43 samples lacked information (Hair, B., B., & Anderson, 2010). The primary sources of data were collected from June 2020 to October 2020 in HCMC. The researchers were surveyed by hard copy distributed. All data collected from the questionnaire are coded, processed by SPSS 20.0 and Amos.

The researchers testing scale reliability with Cronbach’s alpha coefficient and exploratory factor analyses (EFA) were performed by (Hair, B., B., & Anderson, 2010). The purpose of confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) helps the author to clarify: (1) Unilaterality, (2) Reliability of scale, (3) Convergence value, and (4) Difference value. A research model considered relevant to the data if Chi-square testing is P-value > 5%; CMIN/df ≤ 2, some cases CMIN/df maybe ≤ 3 or < 5; GFI, TLI, CFI ≥ 0.9. However, according to recent researchers’ opinions, GFI is still acceptable when it is greater than 0.8; RMSEA ≤ 0.08. Apart from the above criteria, the test results must also ensure synthetic reliability > 0.6; the Average variance extracted must be greater than 0.5 by (Hair, B., B., & Anderson, 2010).

RESEARCH RESULTS

Testing Cronbach’s alpha for factors affecting the quality culture of public secondary schools in Ho Chi Minh City following:

Table 1. Cronbach’s alpha of factors affecting the quality culture of public secondary schools

Cultural environment (CE), Cronbach’s Alpha: 0.940	Authors	Cronbach’s Alpha
CE1: Building codes of conduct in public secondary schools	Bashayreh, A. M., et al. (2016)	0.915
CE2: Respecting, cooperating, and supporting each other among the members for the cause and reputation of public secondary schools	Brychta, K. A. (2019)	0.933

CE3: Practicing ethics, living a healthy lifestyle, preserving and promoting good traditions	Ceidokhti, A. J. and Thaderi, M. T. (2019)	0.927
CE4: Implementation of exchange, cooperation, and integration activities with the domestic and foreign communities	Deepa, M. and Gowtham, S. (2016)	0.909
Natural environment (NAE), Cronbach's Alpha: 0.893	Authors	Cronbach's Alpha
NAE1: The public secondary schools' architecture and landscape are green, clean, beautiful, harmonious, and reasonable	Drinke, V. (2019)	0.818
NAE2: The facilities and equipment are for teaching, practice, and scientific research in terms of quantity and quality	Givarian, H., et al. (2013)	0.873
NAE3: The library ensures good service for teaching, learning, and practicum	Harvey, L. K. (2014)	0.851
Academic environment (AE), Cronbach's Alpha: 0.946	Authors	Cronbach's Alpha
AE1: Develop appropriate strategies, plans, and investments for the proper academic activities for the mission	Hulpiau, L. V., & Verhesschen, P. (2017)	0.911
AE2: Exercise autonomy and social responsibility for academic performance	Manji, G. K., & Sallace, W. K. (2017)	0.945
AE3: Encourage academic cooperation and sharing among public secondary schools	Mendes, J. C., Silva, J. A. (2014)	0.938
AE4: Implement continuously fostering and developing academics for teachers and leaders	Nulland, Y. V. (2016)	0.920
Social environment (SE), Cronbach's Alpha: 0.865	Authors	Cronbach's Alpha
SE1: Build a vision, mission, and goal that is appropriate to the resources and position of public secondary schools	Rad, A. M. (2016)	0.817
SE2: Establish organizational structure and clearly define functions	Rameron, K. T., & Quinn, R. E. (2018)	0.822
SE3: Set up, delineate functions, duties, responsibilities, and powers of functional units in public secondary schools	Rose, R. Y., Kumar, M., Abdullah, H. (2018)	0.853
SE4: Establish the operating mechanism, coordinate activities, and evaluate the effectiveness of functional faculty and others	Seramina, D. H. (2013)	0.821
Humanistic environment (HE), Cronbach's Alpha: 0.851	Authors	Cronbach's Alpha
HE1: Exercise comprehensive democratic rights to the contingent of cadres, faculty, staff, and learners	Suran, J. M., & Godfrey, A. Y. (2016)	0.805
HE2: Fully implementing primary benefits under the state policy regime for the contingent of cadres, lecturers, staff, and learners	Thameron, K., & Sine, M. (2015)	0.802
HE3: Develop mechanisms, policies, and measures for staff, lecturers, staff, and learners to fully implement	Treeman, S. V. and Mishra, A. L. (2017)	0.838
HE4: Develop quality and effective policy on internal responsibility and social responsibility	Trendes, J. C. (2016)	0.799

(Source: Researchers proposed by SPSS 20.0)

Table 1 showed that Cronbach's alpha of the academic environment (AE) is 0.946; for the social environment (SE) is 0.865; for the humanistic environment (HE) is 0.851. They are Cronbach's alpha > 0.6.

Table 2. Cronbach's alpha for the quality culture and pupils' satisfaction

The quality culture (QC), Cronbach's Alpha: 0.850	Authors	Cronbach's Alpha
QC1: Academic environment affecting the quality culture of public secondary schools in HCMC	Trore, T. W. (2015)	0.818
QC2: Social environment affecting the quality culture of public secondary schools in HCMC	Naala, N. I. (2016)	0.785
QC3: Humanistic environment affecting the quality culture of public secondary schools in HCMC	Naureen, R. (2020)	0.841
QC4: Cultural and natural environment affecting the quality culture of public secondary schools in HCMC	Okoli, M. (2019)	0.787
Pupils' satisfaction (PS), Cronbach's Alpha: 0.938	Authors	Cronbach's Alpha
PS1: Pupils are satisfied with the learning environment at the school	Smit, J., A. (2016)	0.929
PS2: Pupils will introduce people to their school	Tewodros Bayeh Tedla (2016)	0.916

PS3: Pupils are very proud of the quality culture at this school	Thomas, P., and Pырros, P. (2018)	0.925
PS4: Pupils feel happy every day when they come to class	Whalen, T. (2020)	0.907

(Source: Researchers proposed by SPSS 20.0)

Table 2 showed that all of Cronbach’s Alpha is greater than 0.7. Table 2 showed that Cronbach’s Alpha for the quality culture (QC) is 0.850; the pupils’ satisfaction (PS) is 0.938.

Source: Researchers proposed

Figure 3.Confirmatory factor analysis for factors affecting the quality culture and pupils’ satisfaction of secondary schools in Ho Chi Minh City

Table 3.Factors affecting the quality culture of secondary schools in HCMC

Relationships	Coe.	Standardized Coefficient	S.E.	C.R.	P
QC <--- AE	0.079	0.139	0.020	3.841	***
QC <--- SE	0.228	0.340	0.033	7.013	***
QC <--- CE	0.074	0.114	0.024	3.121	0.002
QC <--- HE	0.092	0.136	0.027	3.445	***
QC <--- NAE	0.147	0.203	0.033	4.431	***
PC <--- QC	0.308	0.224	0.059	5.261	***

(Source: Researchers proposed by SPSS 20.0 and Amos)

Table 3 showed that column “P” < 0.01 with significance level 0.01. This result indicated that five factors affected secondary schools’ quality culture, affecting pupils’ satisfaction in Ho Chi Minh City with a significance level of 0.01.

Source: Researchers proposed by SPSS 20.0 and Amos
Figure 4. The structural model showing the structural linkage between AE, SE, NAE, HE, CE, QC, and PC

CONCLUSIONS & MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

Conclusions

In general, quality culture in the field of higher education in secondary schools, in particular, has been studied and applied since the early years of the 21st century and mainly in Europe. In Vietnam, only a few universities declare building a quality culture towards quality assurance work. Many researchers and prestigious higher education institutions have affirmed the role of quality culture in the world as a decisive factor for educational institutions' success in the increasingly competitive context. This result was increasing and decreasing the number of learners. Therefore, this paper aims to determine quality culture affecting pupils' satisfaction at ten secondary schools in Ho Chi Minh City. The authors applied a simple random sampling technique. The authors tested Cronbach's Alpha and confirmatory factor analysis and model testing with Structural Equation Modeling. Besides, the study surveyed 600 pupils and answered 27 questions, but 557 samples were processed. The study's findings had five factors affecting the quality culture, which affected pupils' satisfaction with a significance level of 0.01. Research results are an essential scientific basis for Ho Chi Minh City's public secondary schools to refer to and apply in practice to enhance pupils' satisfaction.

Managerial implications

Based on the results mentioned above, to enhance public secondary schools' quality culture and pupils' satisfaction in Ho Chi Minh City.

(1) Managerial implication for the social environment (SE). Public secondary schools need to learn and evaluate school culture's current state regularly. Finding and assessing school culture's current state is a critical job and

extremely difficult. Because quality culture is a collection of all the factors that make up this school's distinctive characteristics, this compared to other schools and other organizations. The manifestations of quality culture are vibrant and complex. Based on expression, the school culture consists of visible highlights such as school landscape space, logos, slogans, communication behaviors, and unobserved sinks such as Beliefs, feelings, and attitudes. Therefore, when authors studied and evaluated the current state of school culture, it is necessary to conduct an objective, scientific, and comprehensive assessment in all aspects.

Quality culture has at school network, vision; Standards, values, and beliefs in schools; The traditions, rituals, and rituals of the school; School history; People and relationships in the school; Architecture, artifacts, and symbols of the school. Moreover, it is necessary to learn and evaluate the objective conditions (economic, socio-political, cultural requirements of the locality, the primary mechanism books) and subjective (perceptions of staff members, students of the role of the culture; working style of the members of the school) affect the cultural environment of the school. Based on the assessment results, the school will have an orientation to preserve and promote its good cultural values and eliminate negative values, inappropriate or hindering the home's development. At the same time, find appropriate solutions to set new standards, new deals of the era. Moreover, it is necessary to learn and evaluate objective conditions (economic conditions, socio-political conditions, local culture, policy mechanisms) and subjective (perceptions of staff, teachers, and students about the role of the quality culture; working style, style of the members in the school) affecting the cultural environment of the school. Based on the evaluation results, the school will have an orientation to preserve and promote the school's good cultural values and eliminate negative values, inappropriate or hindering the development of the home. At the same time, find appropriate solutions to set new standards, new deals of the era. Moreover, it is necessary to learn and evaluate objective conditions (economic conditions, socio-political conditions, local culture, policy mechanisms) and subjective (perceptions of staff, teachers, and students about the role of the quality culture; working style, style of the members in the school) affecting the cultural environment of the school. Based on the assessment results, the school will have an orientation to preserve and promote the school's good cultural values and eliminate negative values, inappropriate or hindering the home's development. At the same time, find appropriate solutions to set new standards, new deals of the era. style, working style of members in the school) affect the cultural environment of the school. Based on the assessment results, the school will have an orientation to preserve and promote its good cultural values and eliminate negative values, inappropriate or hindering the home's development. At the same time, find appropriate solutions to set new standards, new deals of the era. style, working style of members in the school) affect the cultural environment of the school. Based on the assessment results, the school will have an orientation to preserve and promote its good cultural values and eliminate negative values, inappropriate or hindering the home's development. At the same time, find appropriate solutions to set new standards, new deals of the era.

(2) Managerial implication for the natural environment (NAE). Public secondary schools need to improve the natural environment by building. One principle of the learning environment is openness. Be open to yourself, honest to others, free to learning, open to asking questions, open to considering, open to observation. Learners and teachers must be available in their thoughts, feelings, and actions - open to themselves in private spaces, open to oneself in the presence of others, and accessible to others in front of them. This recommendation is crucial because learning takes place in contemplating ourselves, about those around us, and real situations, for example, during a training session on dealing with violence against women in the participation of experienced people. A friendly, safe and healthy learning environment is an environment where students can study in secure facilities; materials and materials used for teaching are suitable for the educational program's objectives and contents, ensuring the science, accuracy, pedagogy, humanity, and aesthetics. Students are allowed to participate in entertainment, culture, arts, physical training, and sports suitable for their age, physiological and psychological characteristics for educational institution members. In particular, students are equipped with knowledge and skills on child abuse prevention and control, school violence, and educational institutions are not adversely affected by the types of businesses and services around them.

(3) Managerial implication for the academic environment (AE). Public secondary schools need to improve the educational setting, such as the training facilities, it must be ensured that the physical and administrative elements (such as food, travel, etc.) of the training are well-coordinated and managed, not causing problems - any stress or anxiety for the learner. Small things are the cleanliness, tidy of the classroom, the preparation or pre-installation of technical aids. The practice of small rooms for group exercises, noise reduction, and room movement (arrival, departure) are essential factors teachers must embrace to ensure that learners do not get disturbed or worry about these issues in the learning process.

(4) Managerial implication for the humanistic environment (HE). Public secondary schools need to raise awareness for all staff, staff, lecturers, and students throughout the school about the role and importance of the school's cultural environment:

Managers need to build a healthy and positive school culture environment. First of all, staff, lecturers, staff, and students need to have a complete, correct, and precise awareness of it; must see the meaning, importance, content, and mode, the way to build school culture; about the relationship between school members; about the current situation as well as the goals, needs, and desires of individuals and organizations in the construction and development of their school culture.

To help all school members see the role, importance, meaning, and impact of the cultural environment in enhancing and developing the quality of training, creating the house's reputation and brand. Schools, schools in general, mass organizations, faculties, and departments, in particular, should organize seminars and clubs to discuss the issue of building healthy and active school culture. Through those workshops, the school members will realize that building a healthy, positive school culture is the mission, goal, responsibility, and interests of each individual and organization in the house. School is the requirement of society. Since then, each individual in the school is aware of his responsibility to build a healthy and positive school culture environment - an environment where he is working and studying.

(5) Managerial implication for the cultural environment (CE). Public secondary schools need to improve their cultural backgrounds, such as safety and psychological comfort. Learners need to be challenged, thinking, not knowledge. Learners need to be stimulated to develop, not lose what there will be. Teachers should ask questions to help learners explore a new experience, not make learners feel like they have no voice. Ability to get support - individual, small group support, enabling people to support each other, just as instructors and instructors can help learners and themselves - non-verbal action. This support should be maintained both during and outside of school hours. The instructor should call on learners to support each other.

A sense of psychological security is an essential aspect of the learning environment: I can be myself; I can be honest with myself; I can see myself; I can challenge myself. I could make a mistake, but the people around me still accept me. Besides, safety is also shown in protecting each other in a group. This commendation will create conditions for learners to open up, take risks, and share about themselves.

Public secondary schools need to use the network of information channels for educational purposes and improve the quality of education: The dissemination and dissemination of information within the organization or from the organization to the outside and vice versa is also considered one of the essential cultural identifiers a school organization. It is vital to make use of the network of information channels to perform all the school's tasks, goals, plans, and activities: To build the image of the school, the school needs to publicize, advertise, and declare its vision, mission, core values, and development strategy on social networks. That is also how to reinforce society's belief in the school's education and training's prestige and quality.

It is necessary to use the network of communication channels to improve the quality and efficiency of all school activities, such as meetings, depending on the purpose and actual conditions of a face-to-face meeting. Conducted online over the internet; Schools continue teaching and learning in the classroom where the teacher and students are facing, which can also be undertaken through google classes, computerized lessons - using software and devices. Convenient to teach, students can again listen to lectures at different times. Information sharing has within the organization should be widely disseminated to all members; everyone needs to be "known" to be "discussed" (information democracy). The communication method is also an organizational culture because it communicates with people: opinions are conveyed directly in two dimensions of democratic dialogue or an authoritarian one-way "commanding," through traditional or present means great.

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